

Instruct-FandanGO

TechEvalCLI User Manual

Version: 0.2

Status: DRAFT

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Overview

The TechEvalCLI in FandanGO is a free and open-source command-line interface (CLI) tool written in Python, designed principally for managing technical evaluations and retrieving related field data. It facilitates interaction between ARIA's access APIs and FandanGO, allowing you to execute access-related actions on the command line. You can view the source code on GitHub page here: <https://github.com/FragmentScreen/fandanGO-aria>

Installation and Setup

The FandanGO TechEvalCLI is a Python 3.0 application, so you must first install Python. You can do this from <https://www.python.org/downloads/>, or if you have [Homebrew](#) installed you can run the command:

```
$ brew install python3
```

Then install the FandanGO ARIA plugin using pip:

```
$ pip install FandanGO-aria
```

Once installed, you'll need to complete the setup instructions. You can find these in the README.md file in the application directory, or on the [FandanGO-ARIA GitHub page](#).

How to use

1. Initiate

If no token is available, log into ARIA:

```
$ goaria login
```

To start the CLI, run:

```
$ goaria tech-eval
```

2. Main Menu

Once the CLI is initialised, the main menu provides the following options:

- Retrieve Visit Fields: Allows you to fetch specific fields related to a visit.
- Submit Visit Evaluation: Prompts you to input evaluation data and submit it.
- Exit: Exits the tool

```
(venv) luiholliday@Luis-MacBook-Pro fandango-aria-plugin % goaria tech-eval
? What would you like to do? (Use arrow keys)
  » Retrieve Visit Fields
    Submit Visit Evaluation
    Exit
```

3. Retrieving Visit Fields

To retrieve fields for a particular visit:

1. Select the Retrieve Visit Fields option.
2. You will be prompted to enter a Visit ID (VID).
3. The CLI will fetch the fields related to that visit and display them.

```
(venv) luiholliday@Luis-MacBook-Pro fandango-aria-plugin % goaria tech-eval
? What would you like to do? Retrieve Visit Fields
Enter Visit ID: 155
[
  {
    "fid": "112",
    "type": "TEXT_SHORT",
    "help": "Please give tech feedback",
    "max": "",
    "opts": "",
    "ref": "Techevalri"
  },
  {
    "fid": "113",
    "type": "TEXT_NUMERIC",
    "help": "Please give num",
    "max": "10",
    "opts": "",
    "ref": "luitestnum"
  }
]
? What would you like to do? (Use arrow keys)
  » Retrieve Visit Fields
    Submit Visit Evaluation
    Exit
```

4. Submitting a Technical Evaluation

To submit an evaluation:

1. Select the Submit Visit Evaluation option.
2. You will be prompted to enter a Visit ID (vid).
3. Confirm whether you accept the evaluation.
4. The CLI will then retrieve the fields related to the visit. If no fields are found, you will return to the main menu.

5. If fields are retrieved, you will be asked to enter a value for each field. The prompt will display the field reference and type.
6. There is validation built into each type, so should reject unacceptable responses on the command line (e.g. 'hello world' for a number field)
7. The CLI will then submit the evaluation, and you will receive a success or failure message.

```
? What would you like to do? Submit Visit Evaluation
Enter VID: 155
Do you accept this evaluation? [y/N]: y

Retrieved Fields:

[
  {
    "fid": "112",
    "type": "TEXT_SHORT",
    "help": "Please give tech feedback",
    "max": "",
    "opts": "",
    "ref": "Techevalri"
  },
  {
    "fid": "113",
    "type": "TEXT_NUMERIC",
    "help": "Please give num",
    "max": "10",
    "opts": "",
    "ref": "luitestnum"
  }
]
Enter value for field 'Techevalri' (type: TEXT_SHORT) : This is a test
Enter value for field 'luitestnum' (type: TEXT_NUMERIC) : 5
Evaluation submitted successfully!
```

Version History

Version	Authors	Description
0.1	Lui Holliday	Initial Draft
0.2	Marcus Lowndes	Reformat and small changes for publishing